

ELABORATE ON THE ADVANTAGES OF LEARNING A SECOND LANGUAGE IN GRADUATE SCHOOL

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Abstract. This article discusses the benefits of studying a second language in graduate school, and identifies the pros and cons of studying a foreign language.

Keywords: foreign language, graduate school, benefits, modern world, process.

The beginning of the XXI century has become a time of serious changes for our country. After independence, Uzbekistan was actively involved in the process of globalization, the main idea of which, from the point of view of social changes, according to most researchers, is a large-scale integration of everything social: "states, peoples, communities, cultures, values, spheres of public life, which contributes to the formation of a world community and an integral planetary system, as well as the unification of public life in various territories, within various communities and social formations, which occurs in parallel with integration" [2]. One of the first in Uzbekistan to be included in the process of integration and unification was the sphere of education as one of the dominant "subsystems of the social whole", largely determining not only "the parameters of the life path of an individual, but also the vectors of development of the state" [3].

Based on the understanding of the general picture of the modern world, and also accepting as a single basis for postgraduate study that upon completion of postgraduate study, the student must meet the qualifications of a research teacher, which formulates the following "global goal" of training highly qualified personnel: "to help young people entering postgraduate study to maximize their research and pedagogical abilities." The Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan emphasizes that the goal of postgraduate education "cannot consist in simply obtaining and deepening professional knowledge," education should be based "on deepening the skills of systematic, methodical and innovative thinking, including the ability to competently and convincingly express one's ideas in Uzbek and foreign languages" [1]. We find confirmation of this idea in the research of E. Shukurova. Discussing the implementation of the goals of modern student-oriented higher education, the author, among others, highlights the following professional competencies of a higher education teacher: "systemic thinking; high level of communication skills; as well as proficiency in multicultural communication (at least two languages)" [3].

The above-listed requirements for a researcher and teacher of higher education are largely implemented through the discipline "Foreign Language". In all the main professional educational programs (MPEP) of higher education, regardless of the direction of training in postgraduate study, the discipline "Foreign Language" is assigned a universal competence: UK-4 - "readiness to use modern methods and technologies of scientific communication in the state and foreign languages", in a number of MPEP we also encounter UK-3 - "readiness to participate in the work of Russian and international research teams to solve scientific and scientific-educational problems". In our opinion, the inclusion of UK-3 in the list of competencies formed in foreign language lessons is quite logical. We believe that both of these competencies are complementary: work in international research teams is impossible without scientific

communication skills in a foreign language, just as the use of modern methods and technologies of scientific communication is hardly possible outside the framework of solving scientific and scientific-educational problems.

Learning a foreign language, no matter your reasons, knowing two or more languages will bring many benefits to your life, and it also has its pros and cons: Pros of learning a new language

1. Networking

The first benefit is quite simple: the more languages you know, the more people you will be able to communicate with. Whether you are moving to a new country, going to study abroad, or just communicating on social networks. A new language will allow you to make friends, share ideas with people you might never have met if you only had your native language to spare. This is the main value of learning languages: you get acquainted with different points of view and thinking of people from different cultures, as well as literature and information on your specialty.

2. Earnings

There is nothing sadder in the world than finding a vacancy that is perfect for you in every way except the requirement to know the language. By learning a second language, you can open the door to new career opportunities. In fact, some studies have shown that bilingual employees are more likely to get promoted and often earn more than monolingual employees.

3. Boost Your Creative Thinking

Learning a new language (and using it) engages your creative thinking. If you don't know how to say something in a foreign language, you have to find other ways to express it: for example, you can use gestures and actions, or simply describe what you want to say. People who speak a second language also approach problem solving more creatively.

4. Supercharge Your Brain

Did you know that learning languages actually improves your brain's cognitive function? There is strong evidence that learning a language actually increases the amount of gray matter in your brain, improving your ability to remember, reason, and solve problems. Learning a language also helps preserve your brain's white matter, meaning you can process information faster. Learning a new language can help slow the onset of dementia as you age.

Cons of learning a new language:

1. Loss of cultural identity

In some cases, especially for young people, learning a second language results in neglecting your native language. For example, you moved to another country and are forced to communicate in another language most of the time (except maybe at home). Eventually, you may begin to "lose" your native language. And since language is closely tied to our cultural identity, this can lead to the feeling that you no longer have a strong connection with your native culture.

2. Not being yourself fully

When communicating in a foreign language, it can be difficult to express your individuality. This is especially difficult when you are just developing your language skills and cannot yet express the same thoughts as in your native language due to an insufficient vocabulary. This means that you will not be able to express certain emotions, shine with intelligence or a sharp sense of humor.

Even those who are quite proficient in the language can face such difficulties. Why? Because each language is unique. For example, your language may have concepts or notions that are related to the culture and history of your country. There may simply be no equivalent to these phrases in the language you are learning: expressing a thought becomes more difficult when the participants in a dialogue do not have a common background.

3. Time Costs

Have you ever heard of the “opportunity cost”? It means . . . basically, it is the price you pay for your hobbies and desires (opportunities). For example, the opportunity cost of going to a concert is equal to the price of a ticket to that concert. But cost is not always measured in money. In the case of language learning, the main currency is time. In other words, becoming bilingual will take some time. And you could spend that time on something else: meeting friends, working more to earn more money, or learning something else, like playing the guitar. Everything has a price!

So, learning a new language will allow you to go beyond the limits. Despite the disadvantages, you can achieve a lot by speaking several languages. Ludwig Wittgenstein said it best: “The limits of my world are the limits of my language”.

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